

Preparation and Spectroscopic Studies of some N-Donor Complexes of Ethyl(n-propyl)tin Dichloride and their Reactions with Benzoyl Chloride

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Hexacoordinated tin(IV) complexes of ethyl(n-propyl)tin dichloride with some N-donors such as pyridine, pyrrolidine, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline have been prepared. Infrared, Raman and Mössbauer techniques have been used to infer stereochemistry around tin atom. The results indicate a *cis*-chlorine arrangement in all these complexes. They themselves are weak electrolytes in nitrobenzene but give ionic products with benzoyl chloride.

In addition to the usual characterisation of the organotin compounds^{1,2}, the antitumour activity³ of many complexes has also been studied. The above activity of the complexes of diorganotin dichlorides has been reported to depend upon the Cl—Sn—Cl bond angle³ and stability of the complex⁴. A broad review of the literature on the complexes of diorganotin dichlorides shows that the mixed ones have drawn comparatively far less attention in comparison to the simple ones, which may be due to the lengthy and difficult procedure required for the preparation of the former type of compounds.

In the present paper the preparation of some complexes of ethyl(n-propyl)tin dichloride with N-donors such as pyridine, pyrrolidine, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline has been reported. They have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, Raman and Mössbauer spectra. Their reactions with benzoyl chloride in nitrobenzene have also been studied.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are white solids and

have sharp melting points. The complexes of unidentate ligands possess 1 : 2 (acid : base) stoichiometry while those of bidentate ligands are equimolar ones.

Infrared studies: Ir spectra of the complexes show many perturbations in the ligand frequencies on complexation⁵⁻⁷. The shifts in their frequencies (Table 1) on complexation clearly indicate the donation of electrons by the nitrogen of the ligand to tin^{5,6}. In addition, the trigonal vibration appearing at 1 029 cm⁻¹ in case of pyridine shifts to 1 035 cm⁻¹ on complexation while ring breathing shifts from 991 to 1 005 cm⁻¹. In case of pyrrolidine, bands at 3 270, 2 941, 2 912 and 2 865 cm⁻¹ assigned to NH and CH stretches shift to 3 150, 2 930 and 2 845 cm⁻¹. The NH deformation (1 640), NH bend (1 412 and 1 397), ring breathing (902) and ring deformation (612 cm⁻¹) bands appear at 1 622, 1 411, 1 377, 910 and 632 cm⁻¹ respectively in its complex. The negative shifts in ν_{NH} , δ_{NH} and $\delta_{\text{H-N-C}}$ frequencies in the ligand on complexation are in the expected direction^{5,8}.

The ir spectra of ethyl(n-propyl)tin dichloride

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA FOR ETHYL(N-PROPYL)TIN DICHLORIDE AND ITS N-DONOR COMPLEXES

Compd*.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Sn—C str.	Sn—Cl str.	C...C and C...N str.	C H deform.	Ring deform.
		Sn	Cl					
EtPr ⁿ SnCl ₂	52—53	46.25 (46.42)	27.80 (27.09)	545 (Raman 558, 520)	348, 320, 295 (Raman 348, 328)	—	—	—
EtPr ⁿ SnCl ₂ .2Py	114—15	28.66 (28.33)	16.53 (16.90)	600, 550, 530, 500	290, 255	1 630, 1 592, 1 503, 1 460	1 208, 1 060, 685	652, 430
EtPr ⁿ SnCl ₂ .5Pyr	109—13	30.78 (30.99)	17.68 (17.93)	552—520	280, 260	—	—	632
EtPr ⁿ SnCl ₂ .Bipy	184—85	28.30 (28.47)	16.58 (16.98)	550—535 (Raman 585, 500)	279, 267, 244 (Raman 265, 242)	1 590, 1 570, 1 559, 1 551, 1 448, 1 440	—	630, 410
EtPr ⁿ SnCl ₂ .Phen	95—96	26.10 (25.87)	15.73 (15.92)	550—540	290, 245	1 586, 1574, 1 512	856, 847, 768, 725	638, 412

*Py=pyridine, Pyr=pyrrolidine, Bipy=2,2'-bipyridyl, Phen=1,10-phenanthroline.

and its complexes in the Sn—C stretching region are complicated because of the possibility of the existence of *n*-propyl group both in *trans* and *gauche* forms with respect to the tin atom. Cummins⁹ assigned the higher frequency band to the *trans*-conformation and the lower one to *gauche*-conformation in a mixture of the two forms present in equilibrium with each other. The appearance of one ir broad band at 545 cm⁻¹ and two Raman bands at 558 and 520 cm⁻¹ (Table 1) indicates the presence of *n*-propyl group in both *trans* and *gauche* forms. Similar inferences may be drawn at least in the case of pyridine and 2,2'-bipyridyl complexes¹¹.

Sn—Cl stretching frequencies of ethyl(*n*-propyl)tin dichloride show a negative shift on complexation (Table 1) as the acceptance of electrons by tin would cause the lengthening of Sn—Cl bond¹¹ and is in parallel with the previous observations¹². The non-linear Cl—Sn—Cl arrangement would cause the splitting of these bands due to the symmetric and asymmetric Sn—Cl stretches. But the appearance of more than two bands in some cases indicates the presence of both *trans* and *gauche* forms of *n*-propyl group.

Mössbauer studies : The isomer shift (IS) values for ethyl(*n*-propyl)tin dichlorides and its complexes with pyridine and 2,2'-bipyridyl are 1.72, 1.08 and 1.59 mm/s respectively. The decrease in IS value on complexation suggests the decrease in *s*-electron density on the tin atom on coordination which may be due to the change in hybridisation of the tin atom from *sp*³ to *sp*³*d*² and involves the reduction of *s*-electron density on the tin atom due to greater shielding by the occupied 5*d*-orbitals¹³.

Quadrupole splitting (QS) value for ethyl(*n*-propyl)tin dichloride is 3.53 mm/s which is comparable to that reported for dimethyltin dichloride and suggests some weak association in the compound at liquid nitrogen temperature¹⁴. For the pyridine complex, QS value has been found to be 2.16 mm/s which suggests that the alkyl groups occupy *cis*-position in the molecule as has been reported for many other six-coordinate compounds¹⁵. Appearance of more than two bands in Sn—C stretching region also points to the same direction. Multiple splitting of Sn—Cl bands suggests *cis*-arrangement for the chlorine atoms (Table 1).

In case of 2,2'-bipyridyl complex the value of QS/IS ratio being 2.45, clearly indicates the higher than four-coordinated environments at tin atom¹⁶. QS value (3.90 mm/s) suggests a *trans*-arrangement of alkyl groups around tin atom, though a small distortion of SnC₂ moiety from linearity as also indicated by its ir spectrum cannot be ruled out. A *cis*-chlorine arrangement may, therefore, be anticipated. A similar inference can also be drawn from its ir spectrum which shows more than two bands in Sn—Cl stretching region (Table 1).

Reactions with benzoyl chloride : The millimolar

solutions of all the complexes in nitrobenzene have very low molar conductance values which indicate their weak ionic character even in a medium of high dielectric constant. The addition of benzoyl chloride, which itself is also a weak electrolyte in nitrobenzene, causes an appreciable increase in conductance of the solution in each case. The initial increase in conductance of the solution may be due to reaction of the type¹⁷,

The conductance continues to increase even after the molar concentration of benzoyl chloride exceeds that of the complex and also that the molar conductance value of the solution in the each case is appreciably higher than the one required for uni-univalent electrolytes when benzoyl chloride is added in excess indicate the replacement of the second ligand molecule by chloride ion. Similar observations have been made in case of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline complexes with the difference that the conductance increases slowly which may be due to the chelate effect¹⁸ making it difficult for the chloride ions to replace the bidentate chelating ligand. The following overall reactions may be suggested taking place in the solution,

where L is a unidentate and L-L is a bidentate ligand molecule.

Formation of hexacoordinated tin anions in the above reactions is supported by the reports in the literature¹⁹. Loss of chloride ion by benzoyl chloride is in parallel with the reported observations²⁰.

Experimental

Petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) was dried before use. Nitrobenzene was purified by the reported method²¹. Pyridine and pyrrolidine were kept over KOH pellets before use. Benzoyl chloride was purified by distilling and again fractionating it over dry magnesium oxide. 2,2'-Bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline (AnalaR) were used as such.

Ethyl(*n*-propyl)tin dichloride was prepared by the reported method²². For the preparation of its complex with pyridine, a solution of the base in petroleum ether was added dropwise to a solution of ethyl(*n*-propyl)tin dichloride in the same solvent till the precipitation was just complete. The resulting white precipitates were washed with the solvent and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes with pyrrolidine, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline were prepared by the same method. Tin and chlorine contents were estimated gravimetrically as SnO₂ and AgCl respectively.

The infrared spectra (nujol) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer using sodium chloride and polythene windows, Raman spectra on a Carey 81 spectrometer fitted with an argon ion laser and Mössbauer spectra taken at 77 K on a Harwell spectrometer equipped with a 256 multi-channel analyser against a $Ba^{119m}SnO_3$ source. Data reduction to the Lorentzian line shapes was done by usual least-square methods. For conductance measurements a millimolar solution of the complex in nitrobenzene was placed in a dip type conductivity cell and kept out of contact with atmospheric moisture. The conductance was measured on a Phillips 9500 conductivity bridge. Its reaction with benzoyl chloride was studied by adding to the above solution about ten times more concentrated solution of benzoyl chloride in small portions and the relative conductance calculated after each addition. The results are in agreement with the progress of the reactions (1)–(3).

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